

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING METHODS

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Annotation: The ways in which English is taught are diverse. Teaching foreign languages requires keeping an eye out for innovative strategies to get kids talking. But a lot of traditional institutions continue to attempt teaching using antiquated materials and techniques. You will never be proficient in English, and there will always be issues. You may simply learn and get better at speaking English by using new techniques. Speaking like a native speaker will be possible for you.

Key words: methodology, English language, training.

It has been a long time since learning a foreign language was limited to absorbing new vocabulary and idioms. The pinnacle of proficiency in grasping a foreign language was reached when one could only translate a Russian sentence into a foreign language through monotonous and tedious memorization of grammar rules. Furthermore, only in the 20th century did our nation's English teaching practices undergo a truly revolutionary revolution, despite the fact that the world has long been familiar with a vast array of foreign language learning ways and techniques. Goals and methods have evolved. Everybody is studying a foreign language these days. Both the number of techniques and the number of persons have expanded in proportion. But every approach has advantages and disadvantages. Even though there have been notable results from using the "classics," the guiding ideas of the old school are still sharply criticized today. The only thing left to wonder is how much it cost to get these outcomes. Generally speaking, learning a language required extensive reading of books, a great deal of time spent translating, reading texts, picking up new vocabulary,

practicing various tasks, and recounting stories. Assignments like writing essays or taking dictations were provided as a way to switch things up.

The classical, or fundamental, technique is one of the earliest. Understanding the nuances and specifics of the fundamentals of a foreign language is the main objective of the classical method, rather than merely learning the language. The establishment of the grammatical foundation of the language under study is the primary goal of the classical method. The intended audience consists of those who are just beginning to learn the fundamentals of English. Those who began learning English in school are highly familiar with this method. It is noteworthy that numerous language universities in Kazakhstan and the bordering republics favor it. Here's a simple plan: learn language and fundamental principles, then apply them to real-world situations and reinforce your understanding through activities. N.A. Bonk is the most well-known practitioner of the conventional approach. Written in partnership with other proponents of the same conventional methodology, her well-known "Bonk textbook" serves as a sort of model. This textbook is still the industry standard despite strong competition from the newest methods emerging from the West. The limited expertise with conversational speaking is the only negative, or rather, a drawback of the classical method. This shortcoming can be addressed by supplementing the traditional approach with additional communicative teaching strategies.

The so-called linguo-sociocultural method is one of these techniques. Those who think that a modern foreign language shouldn't be a collection of lexical and grammatical norms are the ones who support the aforementioned approach. On the other hand, the lack of extra-linguistic influences makes studying English dull and pointless. Followers of the linguo-sociocultural approach elevate learning a foreign language to the status of a communication tool that allows for the expression of oneself in addition to speaking. We can confidently state that a foreign language is a kind of mirror in which the way of life, traditions and customs, culture, and history of the language are reflected, in accordance with the linguo-sociocultural method's tenets.

Nonetheless, according to statisticians' assessments and computations, the communicative approach has emerged as the most well-liked approach for teaching foreign languages in recent years. Both in America and Europe, this method has shown to be quite effective. The communicative technique, which is still sweeping the globe, has arrived in our country and is already a mainstay in the top language universities. The approach is predicated on the fusion of traditional and modern language instruction approaches. As the name implies, a key component of the communicative technique is communication. This method's primary objective is to get over the language barrier. The most important thing is to help someone overcome their fear of speaking or writing in a foreign language, as well as their fear of speaking in general, while also helping them to improve their other language skills, including speaking, writing, reading, and listening. It is important to remember that learning grammar occurs when speaking and interacting in a foreign language. The idea is as follows: students should learn and commit to memory language formulae, expressions, and phrases first, and only then should they analyze the grammatical structures within the phrases they have committed to memory. To put it plainly, the oral advance principle is in effect.

The word itself implies that there is a specific position for communication practice in the communicative approach. The communicative technique aims to improve language proficiency in spoken foreign languages. It's also important to remember that the lesson's structure is directly impacted by the methods used. It's common for teachers to use game scenarios, assign group projects, and create exercises that test students' ability to see mistakes and compare and contrast. Generally speaking, these kinds of exercises activate both memory and logic, which helps you become more adept at thinking critically and metaphorically, which in turn inspires you to communicate your ideas.

The most up-to-date interactive materials for learning English are now accessible thanks to the growth of the modern IT industry: the Internet, TV shows, newspapers, magazines, and computers of the newest generation. Putting what spoken above into practice is crucial. In addition to helping students develop abilities that will be

important in the future, this serves to pique their interest in the history, culture, and customs of the nation where the language is being studied.

Learning is a two-way process that requires active participation from both the teacher and the students. The effectiveness of the learning process is contingent upon the teacher.

It is evident that each teacher chooses his or her work methods and strategies based on personal experience. However, it can be claimed that the use of different strategies within the framework of communicative, inductive, and deductive methodologies yields positive outcomes and surely contributes to raising the efficacy of grammar instruction based on the findings of the experimental and practical work conducted.

The author makes an effort to follow the so-called "mixed" teaching approach. This produces excellent outcomes and enables you to reach your goals.

REFERENCES

1. Беседы об уроке иностранного языка : пособие для студентов педагогич. ин-тов / Е.И. Пассов [и др.]. – Л. : Просвещение, 1975. – 176 с.
2. Бим, И.Л. К вопросу о методах обучения иностранным языкам / И.Л. Бим // ИЯШ. –1974. – № 2. – С. 19–32.
3. Воловин, А.В. Коммуникативный подход к изучению иностранных языков в методических системах Великобритании и США / А.В. Воловин // Коммуникативный подход к изучению иностранных языков : сб. на-уч. трудов. – Вып. 275. – М., 1985. – С. 19–32.